

Sponge assemblages and predicted archetypes in the eastern Canadian Arctic

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Table S1. Shortened synoptic table of the diagnostic (highest fidelity, Φ) species for each of the five clusters resulting from the Isopam algorithm at the second cut off level. Results are separated into species with $\Phi \geq 0.23$ (upper) and $\Phi < 0.23$ (lower). Species are ranked by decreasing fidelities within particular clusters. Boldfaced numbers represent significant associations ($p < 0.01$). The percentage occurrence of the species in a particular cluster is shown in brackets. Only species present in more than one location are listed

	I	II.a	II.b	III.a	III.b
I					
<i>Chondrocladia (Chondrocladia) grandis</i>	0.26 (15)	–	–	<0 (2)	<0 (5)
<i>Bathydorus</i> sp. nov.	0.25 (19)	<0 (3)	<0 (1)	<0.01 (10)	<0 (3)
II.a					
<i>Geodia atlantica</i>	–	0.60 (44)	<0 (1)	–	<0 (3)
<i>Stryphnus fortis</i>	–	0.51 (33)	–	–	<0 (3)
<i>Geodia macandrewii</i>	–	0.48 (37)	<0 (2)	<0 (2)	0.01 (8)
<i>Geodia barretti</i>	<0 (1)	0.38 (44)	0.14 (22)	<0 (12)	<0 (3)
<i>Stelletta normani</i>	–	0.32 (24)	<0 (1)	<0.01 (6)	0.09 (11)
II.b					
<i>Asconema foliata</i>	<0 (1)	0.04 (31)	0.68 (88)	0.06 (35)	<0 (10)
III.a					
<i>Mycale (Mycale) lingua</i>	0.02 (22)	<0 (1)	<0 (7)	0.47 (79)	<0 (19)
<i>Phakellia bowerbanki</i>	<0 (3)	–	0.02 (9)	0.40 (40)	<0 (5)
<i>Polymastia hemisphaerica</i>	–	<0 (7)	0.25 (31)	0.36 (50)	<0 (10)
<i>Forcepia (Forcepia) forcipula</i>	<0 (1)	<0 (6)	0.06 (12)	0.36 (38)	<0.01 (8)
<i>Iophon</i> cf. <i>piceum</i>	<0 (1)	–	0.03 (5)	0.29 (21)	0.02 (5)
<i>Polymastia</i> cf. <i>uberrima</i>	<0 (3)	–	0.12 (18)	0.25 (33)	0.09 (18)
<i>Weberella bursa</i>	<0 (2)	<0 (6)	0.21 (22)	0.24 (31)	<0 (6)
III.b					
<i>Geodia hentscheli</i>	–	–	–	–	0.74 (58)
<i>Geodia parva</i>	<0 (1)	0.02 (13)	<0 (2)	<0 (2)	0.65 (65)
<i>Schaudinnia</i> sp.1	<0 (2)	–	–	<0 (6)	0.62 (52)
Tetillidae	<0 (2)	<0 (9)	<0 (17)	0.22 (46)	0.54 (76)
<i>Stelletta raphidiophora</i>	–	0.10 (14)	–	<0 (4)	0.47 (40)
<i>Thenea</i> spp.	<0 (23)	<0 (11)	<0 (26)	0.39 (96)	0.46 (97)
<i>Geodia phlegraei</i>	–	0.16 (20)	<0 (1)	<0 (6)	0.42 (40)
<i>Desmacella inornata</i>	<0 (3)	<0 (7)	<0 (3)	0.20 (27)	0.26 (29)
Diagnostic species with $\Phi < 0.23$					

	I	II.a	II.b	III.a	III.b
<i>Polymastia thielei</i>	0.03 (17)	–	<0 (9)	0.16 (33)	0.14 (29)
<i>Lissodendoryx (Lissodendoryx) complicata</i>	0.11 (15)	<0 (3)	<0 (5)	<0 (4)	0.11 (19)
Demospongiae	0.12 (10)	<0 (1)	<0 (1)	0.03 (8)	<0.01 (6)
<i>Polymastia grimaldii</i>	0.02 (6)	–	0.11 (11)	0.04 (8)	–
<i>Cladorhiza oxedata</i>	<0 (4)	<0 (1)	0.02 (5)	0.12 (12)	<0 (3)
Iotrochotidae	0.01 (5)	<0 (1)	<0 (1)	0.10 (10)	0.07 (8)
<i>Lissodendoryx (Lissodendoryx) indistincta</i>	0.17 (9)	–	–	0.03 (6)	<0 (2)
<i>Lissodendoryx (Lissodendoryx) lundbecki</i>	0.03 (4)	–	–	0.17 (12)	<0.01 (3)
<i>Biemna variantia</i>	<0 (1)	–	<0 (2)	0.11 (8)	0.15 (10)
<i>Hemigellius arcofer</i>	0.08 (5)	–	0.04 (4)	–	<0 (2)
<i>Artemisina arcigera</i>	0.15 (6)	–	–	<0 (2)	<0 (2)
<i>Tentorium semisuberites</i>	0.07 (4)	–	<0 (1)	0.07 (6)	<0 (2)
<i>Sphaerotylus borealis</i>	<0 (1)	<0 (1)	–	0.13 (8)	0.15 (8)
<i>Polymastia cf. nivea</i>	–	–	0.16 (6)	0.06 (4)	<0 (2)
<i>Forcepia (Forcepia) fabricans</i>	<0 (1)	–	–	0.17 (8)	0.05 (3)
<i>Forcepia (Forcepia) thielei</i>	–	0.18 (7)	0.06 (3)	–	–
<i>Dendoricella aff. flabelliformis</i>	<0 (1)	–	–	0.13 (6)	0.06 (3)
<i>Dendoricella flabelliformis</i>	0.11 (3)	–	–	0.02 (2)	–
<i>Esperiopsis cf. villosa</i>	<0 (1)	–	<0 (1)	0.02 (2)	0.16 (6)
<i>Polymastia andrica</i>	–	–	0.16 (5)	0.07 (4)	–
<i>Tedania cf. suctoria</i>	<0.01 (2)	–	0.03 (2)	0.07 (4)	–
Calcarea	0.10 (3)	–	–	0.02 (2)	–
<i>Lissodendoryx (Ectyodoryx) cf. multiformis</i>	<0 (1)	–	0.09 (3)	0.02 (2)	0.01 (2)
<i>Artemisina aff. apollinis</i>	0.08 (2)	–	–	0.03 (2)	–
<i>Melonanchora cf. elliptica</i>	–	0.07 (3)	<0.01 (1)	0.10 (4)	–
<i>Stylocordyla borealis</i>	0.08 (2)	–	<0.01 (1)	–	–
<i>Axinella arctica</i>	–	0.03 (1)	0.13 (3)	–	–
<i>Calthropella</i> sp. nov.	–	0.22 (6)	–	–	–
<i>Clathria (Clathria) barleei</i>	–	0.03 (1)	0.07 (2)	0.05 (2)	–
<i>Forcepia (Forcepia) forcipis</i>	–	0.03 (1)	0.13 (3)	–	–
<i>Haliclona (Flagellia) porosa</i>	0.06 (2)	–	–	0.05 (2)	–
<i>Lissodendoryx (Ectyodoryx) aff. loyningi</i>	–	–	–	0.20 (6)	0.03 (2)
<i>Mycale (Mycale) loveni</i>	<0 (1)	–	–	0.20 (6)	–
<i>Tethya norvegica</i>	–	0.03 (1)	0.01 (1)	0.12 (4)	–
<i>Chonelasma choanoides</i>	–	0.19 (4)	–	–	–
<i>Forcepia (Forcepia) aff. japonica</i>	–	–	0.03 (1)	–	0.13 (3)
<i>Melonanchora cf. emphysema</i>	–	–	0.09 (2)	0.06 (2)	–
<i>Myxilla brunnea</i>	0.04 (1)	–	–	–	0.05 (2)
<i>Spinularia sarsi</i>	–	–	0.03 (1)	–	0.13 (3)
Suberitidae	–	0.04 (1)	0.09 (2)	–	–
<i>Forcepia</i> sp.2	–	–	–	–	0.17 (3)
<i>Hemigellius cf. pumiceus</i>	–	–	–	0.19 (4)	–
<i>Hymeniacidon</i> spp.	–	–	0.13 (2)	–	–
<i>Janulum spinispiculum</i>	–	0.06 (1)	0.05 (1)	–	–
<i>Mycale (Mycale) cf. arctica</i>	–	0.06 (1)	–	–	0.07 (2)
<i>Polymastia</i> sp.1	–	–	–	–	0.17 (3)
Rosselidae sp.1	0.01 (1)	–	–	0.09 (2)	–

Table S2. The estimated coefficients (Coeff), standard errors (SE) and relative standard errors (RSE) for the component GLMs of the best performing model used to predict each sponge species archetypes (SA). RSE is the SE of the parameter (absolute value) multiplied by 100 and divided by the estimated coefficient. avg: average; b: bottom; chl; chlorophyll *a*; max: maximum; pp: primary production; ran: range; spr: spring; sq: square; sum: summer; tmp: temperature

	(Intercept)			b tmp max avg			b tmp max avg.sq			chl spr max			depth		
	Coeff	SE	RSE	Coeff	SE	RSE	Coeff	SE	RSE	Coeff	SE	RSE	Coeff	SE	RSE
SA1	-1.31	0.07	5.32	2.13	0.41	19.38	-1.71	0.36	21.34	-0.10	0.07	69.14	2.50	0.41	16.45
SA2	-3.80	0.22	5.88	3.17	0.92	28.90	-1.32	0.76	57.85	-0.24	0.13	55.72	-1.97	0.54	27.24
SA3	-3.49	0.16	4.50	6.88	0.74	10.78	-6.37	0.66	10.40	-0.83	0.20	24.23	6.66	0.74	11.09
SA4	-2.89	0.08	2.87	-0.91	0.44	48.45	0.32	0.44	137.62	-0.17	0.12	67.57	1.22	0.38	31.27
SA5	-4.88	0.07	1.51	0.65	0.33	50.13	-0.69	0.30	44.22	-0.03	0.06	220.00	-0.55	0.35	63.75
SA6	-2.53	0.11	4.15	1.63	0.36	22.35	-1.21	0.32	26.56	0.10	0.06	59.19	-0.49	0.45	91.29
	depth.sq			pp_sum_max_avg			pp_sum_max_avg.sq			pp_sum_ran_avg			slope		
	Coeff	SE	RSE	Coeff	SE	RSE	Coeff	SE	RSE	Coeff	SE	RSE	Coeff	SE	RSE
SA1	-2.57	0.43	16.71	1.94	0.78	40.19	-3.00	0.80	26.73	0.83	0.19	22.41	0.18	0.07	38.12
SA2	2.05	0.50	24.63	1.54	1.38	89.61	-0.55	1.28	233.01	-0.63	0.32	50.56	0.17	0.18	110.45
SA3	-5.85	0.70	11.91	-3.49	0.82	23.49	3.49	0.85	24.27	-0.33	0.24	74.26	-0.24	0.11	46.67
SA4	-0.88	0.36	41.19	1.17	0.90	76.89	-1.55	0.97	62.13	0.29	0.20	67.66	-0.01	0.07	1089.41
SA5	0.03	0.39	1129.72	-0.30	0.83	278.73	0.22	0.85	389.99	0.21	0.17	80.45	-0.03	0.09	265.30
SA6	-0.58	0.56	96.94	0.64	0.96	149.60	-1.09	0.99	90.49	0.50	0.19	36.88	0.18	0.09	48.96

Table S3. Species archetype (SA) composition and measures of predictive performance per species (p: significance level; AUC: Area Under the ROC Curve). The number of occurrences (N) and species archetype membership probability (τ) to each SA is indicated for each sponge species. Significance codes: ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05

Species	n	SA1 τ	SA2 τ	SA3 τ	SA4 τ	SA5 τ	SA6 τ	Kendall cor.	p	AUC
SA1										
<i>Geodia parva</i>	54	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.327	***	0.857
<i>Desmacella inornata</i>	45	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.196	***	0.732
<i>Geodia phlegraei</i>	43	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.198	***	0.739
<i>Schaudinnia</i> sp.1	38	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.312	***	0.899
<i>Stelletta raphidiophora</i>	37	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.252	***	0.826
<i>Geodia hentscheli</i>	36	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.337	***	0.942
SA2										
<i>Iophon</i> cf. <i>piceum</i>	18	0	0.983	0.0169	0	0	0	0.172	***	0.813
<i>Lissodendoryx (Lissodendoryx) indistincta</i>	16	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.184	***	0.853
<i>Biemna variantia</i>	14	0	0.9979	0	0	0	0.0021	0.098	*	0.701
<i>Tentorium semisuberites</i>	13	0	0.9999	0	0	0	0.0001	0.102	**	0.716
<i>Artemisina arcigera</i>	11	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.094	*	0.716
<i>Hemigellius arcofer</i>	11	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.074	–	0.671
<i>Sphaerotylus borealis</i>	11	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.070	–	0.661
<i>Polymastia</i> cf. <i>nivea</i>	9	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.036	–	0.592
<i>Forcepia (Forcepia) thielei</i>	8	0	0.9999	0	0.0001	0	0	–0.046	–	0.625
<i>Dendoricella</i> aff. <i>flabelliformis</i>	7	0	0.9999	0	0	0	0.0001	–0.037	–	0.606
<i>Dendoricella flabelliformis</i>	7	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.027	–	0.578
<i>Esperiopsis</i> cf. <i>villosa</i>	7	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.055	–	0.659
<i>Forcepia (Forcepia) fabricans</i>	7	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.098	*	0.780
<i>Polymastia andrica</i>	7	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.066	–	0.689
<i>Lissodendoryx (Ectyodoryx) cf. multiformis</i>	6	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.079	*	0.746
<i>Tedania</i> cf. <i>suctoria</i>	6	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.090	*	0.778
<i>Artemisina</i> aff. <i>apollinis</i>	5	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.014	–	0.546
<i>Melonanchora</i> cf. <i>elliptica</i>	5	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.008	–	0.473
<i>Stylocordyla borealis</i>	5	0	1	0	0	0	0	–0.074	–	0.752

Species	n	SA1	SA2	SA3	SA4	SA5	SA6	Kendall	p	AUC
		τ	τ	τ	τ	τ	τ	cor.		
<i>Axinella arctica</i>	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.053	–	0.699
Calcarea	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.127	***	0.981
<i>Calthropella</i> sp. nov.	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	–0.025	–	0.594
<i>Clathria</i> (<i>Clathria</i>) <i>barleei</i>	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.046	–	0.675
<i>Forcepia</i> (<i>Forcepia</i>) <i>forcipis</i>	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.025	–	0.594
<i>Lissodendoryx</i> (<i>Ectyodoryx</i>) aff. <i>loyningi</i>	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.059	–	0.724
<i>Mycale</i> (<i>Mycale</i>) <i>loveni</i>	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	–0.004	–	0.516
<i>Tethya norvegica</i>	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.053	–	0.699
<i>Chonelasma choanoides</i>	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	–0.059	–	0.756
<i>Forcepia</i> (<i>Forcepia</i>) aff. <i>japonica</i>	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.001	–	0.506
<i>Melonanchora</i> cf. <i>emphysema</i>	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.043	–	0.690
<i>Myxilla brunnea</i>	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.081	*	0.854
<i>Spinularia sarsi</i>	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.023	–	0.603
Suberitidae	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.007	–	0.531
<i>Forcepia</i> sp.2	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.022	–	0.616
<i>Haliclona</i> (<i>Flagellia</i>) <i>porosa</i>	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.077	*	0.910
<i>Hemigellius</i> cf. <i>pumiceus</i>	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.062	–	0.834
<i>Hymeniacidon</i> spp.	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.067	–	0.858
<i>Janulum spinispiculum</i>	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.026	–	0.641
<i>Mycale</i> (<i>Mycale</i>) cf. <i>arctica</i>	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	–0.009	–	0.546
<i>Polymastia</i> sp.1	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000	–	0.502
Rosselidae sp.1	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.016	–	0.587
cf. Axinellidae sp.1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	–0.024	–	0.684
cf. <i>Chaunangium</i> sp.1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	–0.011	–	0.582
cf. Crellidae sp.1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	–0.001	–	0.506
cf. Myxillidae sp.1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.016	–	0.620
<i>Crella</i> (<i>Yvesia</i>) <i>pyrula</i>	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.066	–	1.000
<i>Esperiopsis</i> sp.1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000	–	0.501
<i>Forcepia</i> sp.1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.016	–	0.618
<i>Forcepia</i> sp.3	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.048	–	0.864

Species	n	SA1 τ	SA2 τ	SA3 τ	SA4 τ	SA5 τ	SA6 τ	Kendall cor.	p	AUC
<i>Haliclona (Gellius) varia</i>	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.063	–	0.976
<i>Hamacantha (Vomerula) aff. falcula</i>	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	–0.023	–	0.677
Ietrochotidae sp.1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	–0.010	–	0.576
<i>Isodictya aff. palmata</i>	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.066	–	0.996
<i>Lissodendoryx (Lissodendoryx) stipitata</i>	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.053	–	0.897
<i>Lycopodina cupressiformis</i>	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.064	–	0.982
<i>Mycale (Mycale) cf. toporoki</i>	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.051	–	0.888
<i>Myxilla (Myxilla) fimbriata</i>	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.045	–	0.842
Poeciloscleridae sp.1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	–0.008	–	0.563
<i>Polymastia mamillaris</i>	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	–0.021	–	0.657
<i>Rhizaxinella</i> sp.1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	–0.007	–	0.552
<i>Semisuberites cribrosa</i>	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.026	–	0.699
<i>Sphaerotylus capitatus</i>	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.005	–	0.534
<i>Spinularia cf. sarsi</i>	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	–0.057	–	0.934
<i>Tedania</i> sp.1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.030	–	0.725
SA3										
<i>Mycale (Mycale) lingua</i>	98	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.251	***	0.716
<i>Polymastia hemisphaerica</i>	64	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.311	***	0.817
<i>Polymastia cf. uberrima</i>	48	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.225	***	0.759
<i>Weberella bursa</i>	47	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.251	***	0.791
<i>Forcepia (Forcepia) forcipula</i>	38	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.209	***	0.768
<i>Phakellia bowerbanki</i>	35	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.192	***	0.754
SA4										
<i>Geodia barretti</i>	62	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.358	***	0.869
<i>Geodia atlantica</i>	34	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.327	***	0.940
<i>Geodia macandrewii</i>	34	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.292	***	0.893
<i>Stelletta normani</i>	28	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.211	***	0.811
<i>Stryphnus fortis</i>	25	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.268	***	0.915
SA5										
<i>Thenea</i> spp.	184	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.390	***	0.781

Species	n	SA1 τ	SA2 τ	SA3 τ	SA4 τ	SA5 τ	SA6 τ	Kendall cor.	p	AUC
<i>Asconema foliata</i>	130	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.314	***	0.746
Tetillidae	94	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.365	***	0.819
<i>Polymastia thielei</i>	73	0	0	0	0	0.9999	0.0001	0.165	***	0.659
SA6										
<i>Lissodendoryx (Lissodendoryx) complicata</i>	50	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.247	***	0.779
<i>Bathydorus</i> sp. nov.	47	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.245	***	0.785
<i>Chondrocladia (Chondrocladia) grandis</i>	30	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.216	***	0.808
Demospongiae	28	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.107	**	0.658
<i>Polymastia grimaldii</i>	24	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.005	–	0.492
<i>Cladorhiza oxeata</i>	21	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.020	–	0.534
Iotrochotidae	21	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.066	–	0.611
<i>Lissodendoryx (Lissodendoryx) lundbecki</i>	16	0	0.0083	0	0	0	0.9917	0.071	–	0.636

Fig. S1. Correlation matrix based on Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (ρ) between all predictor variables available in the eastern Canada Arctic. ann: annual; avg: average; b: bottom; chl; chlorophyll *a*; cur: current; max: maximum; min: minimum; mld: mixed layer depth; pp: primary production; ran: range; s: surface; sal: salinity; shr: shear; spr: spring; sum: summer; tmp: temperature; win: winter